

Reduced Precision Redundancy in a Radix-4 FFT Implementation on a Field Programmable Gate Array

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Abstract—Reduced Precision Redundancy (RPR) is demonstrated as a new method for improving fault tolerance in Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) replacing Triple Modular Redundancy (TMR) to protect against the Single Event Effects due to radiation in arithmetic processes.¹² As a test of this approach, the RPR technique was used to implement a Radix-4 Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). This design was implemented in a Xilinx Virtex 2[®] FPGA in order to find the possible gain in speed and reduction in power and resources as compared to the TMR method. Simulation of different degrees of RPR explore the impact on speed and power on the FPGA performance at various levels of precision reduction.

This paper deals with a 64-point 32-bit 3-stage Radix-4 in-place FFT based on an improved FFT algorithm. The whole FFT structure was implemented based on modules designed by the author and Virtex 2[®] FPGA's modules. The implementation of the FFT was successful and was able to handle data in real time at a throughput rate (sample rate) of 134 MHz in simulation.

Based on this FFT design, the implementation of TMR and RPR modules was attempted. First, the TMR structure was designed, creating three identical replicas of the FFT and installing a TMR Voter per FFT's stage. The implementation of this design was not possible due to resource requirements just exceeding the capabilities of the FPGA. The next step was the alteration of the existing FFT and the creation of a smaller 14-bit Butterfly module (BF) for the bound-computing portion of the RPR structure. After the successful completion of this step, we advanced to the implementation of an RPR module with a 14-bit reduced precision bound and a 32-bit precise value (RPR degree 14/32). This design employed a new approach to RPR where two copies of the truncated lower bound are computed separately from the precise value. The degree 14/32 RPR, Radix-4, 3-stage pipeline FFT functioned correctly and was able to work in real time handling data at a throughput of 163 MHz

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	1
BACKGROUND	2
THE FFT DESIGN	3
THE TMR IMPLEMENTATION	9
THE RPR ARCHITECTURE	9
RESULTS, CONCLUSIONS, AND FUTURE WORK	11
REFERENCES	13

INTRODUCTION

Modern satellites are capable of handling controls, communications, observation systems, and on-board payload data processing tasks. The inaccessibility of a satellite after launch and the need for periodic updates of the satellite's data handling procedures create a strong argument for using field programmable gate array (FPGA) instead of application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) technologies. The fact that an FPGA can be reconfigured at any time is a major advantage and the main reason that they are preferred over ASICs in a spacecraft circuit design.

In space systems, radiation can cause unwanted effects, such as the flipping of a memory cell's state in semiconductor devices, better known as soft errors or single event upsets (SEU). FPGAs are susceptible to errors in both data and architecture configuration caused by SEU. In order to prevent this faulty behavior, triple modular redundancy (TMR) is commonly used to ensure reliable operation. However, TMR is very costly in terms of chip area and power consumption.

At the Naval Postgraduate School (NPS), a new method of fault tolerance was introduced in 2006, referred to as reduced precision redundancy (RPR) [1]. RPR applies redundancy only to the most significant numerical bits of a calculation and in this way significantly decreases the needed chip area and power consumption over that required for TMR. Of course, RPR does not guarantee a full precision correct result; a corrected result may only agree with the full precision result in the most significant bits.

¹ U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright
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In order to demonstrate the effectiveness of RPR, the technique is used to implement a Radix-4 Fast Fourier transform (FFT). This design is implemented with different degrees of RPR in a Xilinx Virtex II FPGA in order to find possible improvements in chip area, speed, and power consumption compared with the TMR method.

BACKGROUND

This paper is based on the dissertation of Joshua D. Snodgrass [1] and on two theses, from Nikolaos Gkikas [2] and Margaret A. Sullivan [3], respectively. These works provide valuable information and results that are combined in the design efforts examined in this paper.

Gkikas describes the design of a Radix-4 FFT for wireless communications (wireless local area networks (LANs)) [2]. He compared different algorithm structures based upon the complexity, memory needs, data flow, and controller complexity of each, searching for the most suitable algorithm for his intended application. The design adapted for this demonstration is taken from Gkikas' work, and has three pipeline Butterflies, one for each of the three stages. This design will operate in real time, taking input samples at the basic clock rate of the FPGA realization.

Based on Snodgrass' dissertation [1], Sullivan illustrates the application of RPR as a new method of fault tolerance in FPGAs against single event effects [3]. She examines the use of different degrees of RPR depending on the arithmetic operation and compares the impact of implementation of those degrees to area consumption. A significant conclusion from her work is that the use of RPR instead of TMR in the addition/subtraction operation does not guarantee less area occupancy in every case. After checking the results of FPGA's area comparison, she confirms that "... in order for RPR to be a more desirable fault-tolerance approach than TMR for a simple operation like addition or subtraction, the degree of RPR must be significantly less than 0.5 - and that for both the adder and the voter in a RPR addition process to be smaller than the analogous TMR modules the degree of RPR must be less than 0.25 [3]."

Moreover, she concludes that for the multiplication operation "... a RPR multiplication module requires 1/3 to 1/2 the FPGA slices of a TMR multiplication module depending on the degree of RPR [3]." However, the size of the multiplication RPR voter is extremely large when compared to the TMR voter module, a drawback that should not be underestimated. Another crucial question that she tries to answer is the dilemma of whether to test intermediate results or just the final result for error. She points out, "Any benefit of testing intermediate results in RPR processes must be considered against the additional space it requires [3]."

Later, she explains the basics of a FFT algorithm and reveals thoughts about different ways of implementing a RPR voter in a FFT. According to those thoughts, "...we may include one or more voters on the final or intermediate results [3]." Therefore, there are many choices; for example, we can implement a voter after each multiplication, or after each complex product or maybe at the end of each stage. She predicts that using an 8/32 degree of RPR in a FFT BF operation instead of a TMR will save 66 percent of occupied FPGA slices.

In addition to the theses discussed above, various papers, application reports and notes were also considered in this work. The following notes are not an abstract from these reports. Only the ideas and thoughts that were considered useful for the design are discussed.

In [4], Wu describes the implementation of a Radix-4 DIF FFT using the Texas instrument TMS320C80 digital signal processor (DSP). Although the report is dated, it reveals basic FFT implementation principles in a parallel processor and points out possible errors and/or hazards due to data overflow. In [5], Delphin of ST Industries describes the implementation of the Radix-4 FFT Algorithm using the ST120 DSP. There she explains the basic structure of an FFT Radix-4 and a new algorithm that is derived from the Cooley and Tukey algorithm [6]. She discusses the correct order and the characteristics of each stage BF's factors and twiddle numbers.

There are three relevant papers that discuss the design and implementation improvements of a Radix-4 FFT algorithm in a FPGA. Each of them provides important advice concerning the structure of the design considered in this paper. In the first paper [7], Sun, Liu and Ji give a detailed description of the FFT's memory structure, RAM storage capabilities and restrictions of RAM used in a FPGA. They consider a new way of handling data addresses to allow manipulation of four input and output data streams, while at the same time, bypassing the limitations of modern two-port RAM hardware. In the second paper [8], Bouguezel discusses the profits of using the improved Radix-4 FFT algorithm in comparison to the Cooley-Tukey FFT algorithm [6]. In the third paper [9], Chao, Qin, Yingke and Chengde work on the design of a high performance FFT processor, based on a FPGA. They introduce two important ideas for the optimization of the FPGA. The first idea is the lifting scheme, which is a transform that reduces the number of real multiplications in a BF from four to three. While of benefit, note that it also increases the number of real additions from two to three. The second idea is the use of an adaptive overflow calculation. This novel approach ensures that no overflow takes place over the entire calculation. This is performed without limiting the data path width or decreasing the efficiency of the BF.

THE FFT DESIGN

In order to evaluate RPR concepts in a FFT, many aspects are considered in choosing an implementation. The final choice for this thesis is a 64-point Radix-4 in-place DIF FFT implementation in the Virtex-2 XC2V6000 FPGA.

The objective is to create an FFT that contains only modules which are designed in a Xilinx environment for a Virtex II FPGA XC2V-6000.

The structure of the interconnection of the BF with memory in order to make a radix-4 64-point FFT is shown in Figure 1.

The FFT implementation contains three identical stage modules, one main controller and a last-stage reversing module, as shown in Figure 2. It receives as input a vector of 32-bit complex numbers, which are fixed-point, two's complement numbers. It produces as outputs a vector of 32-bit complex frequency values.

According to analysis conducted for this paper and based on an application report from Cheng [10], there is the possibility of a 3-bit overflow per stage, meaning a 9-bit overflow for the entire 3-stage FFT. In order to avoid overflow issues, a simple solution was chosen. Input numbers were scaled to have values less than 2^{-9} .

All three stages are constructed identically, are pipelined, and their latency is 85 clock cycles per stage. These three stages are depicted in Figure 3. They include a stage controller, a Random-Access Memory (RAM), a compute factor, a BF multiplier and a multiplexer module. The stage controller generates addresses, the RAM receives those addresses and the input signals and sends the output signals to the compute factor. The compute factor computes the factors and sends them to the BF multiplier or to the multiplexer. The BF multiplier performs the necessary multiplications and sends the data to the multiplexer. The multiplexer chooses between incoming data from the compute factor or from the BF multiplier.

Stage Controller. The stage controller receives three and exports four signals. The stage controller of each stage waits for the write enable (WE) signal of the main controller. From this time on, it enters into a continuous process of creating input and output addresses for RAM, based on the algorithm depicted in Figure 1. It also generates the addresses for the ROM's twiddle factors and the switch command for the multiplexer.

RAM. The RAM module contains a ROM memory with the needed twiddle factors and two 128-point, 32-bit RAM from the Xilinx CORE Generator tool. The RAM is the only part of the design that is made with the CORE Generator. The RAM receives 3 addresses, one for the incoming input signals, one for the required output signal

and one for the required twiddle factors. Each of the real and imaginary input signals are stored in one half of the RAM and are exported only when the complete 64-point signals are collected. The RAM module exports four signals, the real and imaginary signal and the real and imaginary twiddle factor. Note that the ROM's stored twiddle factors are not rounded.

Compute Factor. The compute factor has four inputs and five outputs. It needs four pairs of signals in order to compute the proper factors and starts the procedure after commanded by the main controller. It computes three pairs of factors that are sent to the butterfly and a pair of signals that are ready for the next stage. This pair of signals bypasses the BF multiplier and goes directly to the multiplexer.

BF Multiplier. The BF multiplier is the most complicated module of the design. It receives 7 inputs, among them a pair of input factors from the compute factor and a pair of twiddle factors from RAM. It outputs the real and imaginary part of the computed signal.

The aim is to compute the parts of the basic FFT equation. This is demonstrated by the following computation:

$$\begin{aligned} B_r &= factor_1 * W_{N_r}^n + factor_4 * W_{N_{im}}^n \\ B_{im} &= factor_4 * W_{N_r}^n - factor_1 * W_{N_{im}}^n \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Thus, four multiplications and two additions are required. For each multiplication, the Virtex II embedded pipelined multiplier, MULT18x18S, is used. This choice was made to ensure maximum possible speed for our pipelined FFT. This was based on the fact that the embedded multipliers are probably faster than any behavioral multiplier that could be designed for this work. The disadvantage of this choice is the limited number of bits for each multiplier. The Virtex II embedded multiplier can handle 18-bit signed two's complement numbers and outputs a 36-bit result. However, the input signals in this design are 32-bit long. This requires the use of four embedded multipliers for each multiplication. To illustrate, computation of the first product, $factor_1 * W_{N_r}^n$ is shown in Figures 4, 5, and 6, with Figure 4 showing the overall structure of the 32-bit composite multiplier. It can be observed that after the import of the two 32-bit long signals, a factor and a twiddle factor, four different outputs are received from the embedded multipliers. Next, the signal is subject to the concatenation or addition of bits in order to secure the correct multiplication of the signed fixed point numbers. Finally, in the third stage three 64-bit long signals are produced.

Figure 1. Sixty-four-Point Radix-4 In-Place DIF FFT

Figure 2. Sixty-four-Point Radix-4 In-Place DIF Signed Fixed Point 32Bit FFT—The Upper Level

Figure 4. Multiplier—Overview—Part1 & Part2 & Part3

32X32 PIPELINED MULTIPLIER

Figure 5. BF Multiplier—Use of Embedded Multipliers—Part I

Figure 6. BF Multiplier—CSA module—Part2

preference is to export them in the in-place random order and indicate the correct order by using an address monitor.

THE TMR IMPLEMENTATION

The purpose of this paper is to compare the resource requirements and efficiency of the SEU error protection of RPR versus TMR for the arithmetic portions of the 32-bit

fixed point FFT. Our studies and simulation only protected the Compute-factor, BF-multiplier, and Multiplexor-A of each of the three stages, as depicted in figure 3. To fully protect the FFT, in either RPR or TMR, the controller-of-BF –stages module must be triplicated and voted, as RPR techniques do not work on decision logic (a decision is either true or false, there is no “lower precision” answer.) To protect the RAM module in either the TMR or RPR

implementation, the most elegant solution would be to implement single error correcting, double error detecting coding with the error circuitry triplicated. In this case, the fully protected circuit would require the same resources for this portion, whether the arithmetic portions of the circuit are protected by TMR or RPR, and in the TMR case, three sets of RAM would be required.

A TMR 64-point Radix-4 in place DIF was designed and then implemented in the Virtex-2 XC2v6000 FPGA. Note that the voter architecture in both cases (TMR and RPR) must be equivalent. In any other configuration a comparison would be ineffective.

The design of a TMR is a simple process when compared to the design of a RPR. The only significant design decision is to select the number and position of the voters. The options range from triplicating and voting after every logical operation (each AND and OR gate would appear three times, with an XOR gate to vote the results) to three copies of the entire FFT and one voter. As the frequency of the check points increases, the protection effectiveness increases. But, the increased use of voters raises the capacity demand of the design. A good compromise position for voters is to use one voter per FFT stage. The practical implication is that only three voters are required for a 64-point Radix-4 FFT.

At the conclusion of the implementation effort, a successful 64-point Radix-4 in-place DIF in a Virtex-2 XC2v6000 FPGA was designed and implemented. The resources that were used at this time were much less than 12 percent of the slice resources of the FPGA, except for one, the embedded 18 x 18 pipelined multipliers. Exactly $3 \times 4 \times 4 = 48$ embedded multipliers are required for each of the three FFTs. Since there are 144 embedded multipliers available in the XC2v6000 FPGA it seemed as if the TMR design would fit perfectly. Unfortunately, the block RAM modules on the XC2v6000 FPGA share routing resources with the embedded multipliers, so only 138 multipliers are available—the TMR design will not fit! In order to complete the comparisons, the design was simulated on the larger Virtex II XC2V8000 FPGA and this simulation is discussed in the final section.

THE RPR ARCHITECTURE

In the primary design of the FFT, the overflow problem was recognized and the simplest solution was implemented. Therefore, the input was restricted to normalized signals with values less than 2^{-9} .

Our goal in using RPR protection for the FFT is to obtain similar protection to that achieved by Sullivan in her 8-bit bounds with 32-bit precise results for a degree of RPR of 8/32. However, if the inputs to the FFT are to be limited to

magnitudes of less than 2^{-9} , then the upper bound of 2^{-8} will not provide any protection for the output of the FFT.

The solution to this problem was to increase the degree of RPR to 14/32. While an increase of the RPR degree is not desirable because of the added resources required, it is attractive because it minimizes alteration of the primary module. An RPR module was created, using the primary design as its core, with RPR voters embedded at the end of each of the three FFT stages. This design consists of one precise module unit and two smaller low precision module units. The precise module unit is essentially the module described in figures 4, 5, and 6 and handles 32-bit real and imaginary inputs, while outputting 32-bit real and imaginary results. The bound module units are identical and not distinct upper and lower bound units, as was the practice in the earlier work of Snodgrass and Sullivan [1, 4].

The RPR bound module truncates the 32-bit real and imaginary input into a 14-bit number. The 14-bit number passes through the modified compute factor module and enters the modified BF multiplier. Inside the BF multiplier, due to the need for a 14 x 14 bit multiplier instead of the 32 x 32 bit precise module's multiplier, only one 18 x 18 embedded multiplier was used instead of four. There was no need for CSA or CLAH and the result of the multiplication occurred sooner than expected from the precise module unit. In order to keep the program synchronized, a delay was used after the 14 x 14 BF multiplier.

The major difference between the RPR module designs of Snodgrass and Sullivan and this RPR implementation was the altered approach of the RPR function. Instead of using an upper and lower bound, two identical bounds were used that handle the truncated 14-bit value of the 32-bit input. At the end of each stage, the voter inspects the duplicate truncated values and proceeds to a simple bit by bit comparison. If the values are identical, then the voter computes the expected upper and lower limits based on the truncated 14-bit output and on the theoretical expected errors as shown in Equation 4.

$$factor_{Precise} = A_{Precise} + B_{Precise} - C_{Precise} - D_{Precise}$$

$$factor_{Trunc} = A_{Trunc} + B_{Trunc} - C_{Trunc} - D_{Trunc} = \Psi$$

$$\begin{aligned} factor_{Trunc_Up} &= (A_{Trunc} + 1'b1) + (B_{Trunc} + 1'b1) \\ &\quad - C_{Trunc} - D_{Trunc} \\ &= \Psi + 2'b10 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} factor_{Trunc_Lo} &= A_{Trunc} + B_{Trunc} - (C_{Trunc} + 1'b1) \\ &\quad - (D_{Trunc} + 1'b1) \\ &= \Psi - 2'b10 \end{aligned}$$

In the worst possible case,

$$\Psi - 2b'10 \leq factor_{Precise} \leq \Psi + 2b'10 \quad (3)$$

Using the same method,

$$Real_{Precise} = factor_{Precise} * W_{N_Precise}^{real} \\ \pm factor_{Precise} * W_{N_Precise}^{imag}$$

$$Real_{Trunc} = factor_{Trunc} * W_{N_Trunc}^{real} \\ \pm factor_{Trunc} * W_{N_Trunc}^{image} \\ = \Phi$$

Trying to compute the worst possible case, (2)*1 + (3)*1:

$$\Phi - 3'b100 \leq Real_{Precise} \leq \Phi + 3'b100 \quad (4)$$

The voter compares the precise value to the expected upper and lower bounds and decides to choose either the precise value or the average (truncated) value.

In order to verify the truth of the outputs of the implemented FFT structure, a MATLAB FFT simulation file was created. This file was used to compare the output forms of the three different sub-programs. The first subprogram was actually the built-in MATLAB FFT, the second was a clone of the Verilog design in the MATLAB environment, and the third was a MATLAB translator for the implemented FFT results. Since MATLAB usually handles 64-bit numbers and due to the decision for 3-bit shifting of the input in every stage of the FFT, a possible error was identified in the precise calculation of the FFT between MATLAB's calculated outputs and Verilog's translated outputs. These expected errors are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Expected Errors of Precision Calculation

FFTs Outputs	Expected Error
Output of the 1 st Stage	$\leq 2^{-25}$
Output of the 2 nd Stage	$\leq 2^{-22}$
Output of the 3 rd Stage	$\leq 2^{-19}$

The purpose of the entire design was the testing of the implemented FFT in a radiation environment. For this paper, testing was only conducted via simulation of possible radiation effects. To accomplish this, a "radiation" module was added to the FFT design that was capable of introducing error bits at the beginning of each stage, prior to the butterfly calculations.

The radiation module allows great flexibility in the introduction of error bits, giving the ability to decide in which stage, in which module (one of the truncated RPR or

the precise value) and for how long this "form" of radiation lasts. Errors introduced in the first stage have less impact on the precision of the average RPR in contrast to errors introduced in the last stage as shown in Table 2, again due to the three-bit per stage shifting decision. Because of our choice of a 14/32 RPR, the error in the final answer will be limited to 2^{-11} (2^{-14} less the three bits of overflow.)

Table 2. Errors Expected Due to the Import of Radiation in the Precise Module

Radiation introduced in the precise module	Expected Error
Radiation introduced in the 1 st stage	$\leq 2^{-7}$
Radiation introduced in the 2 nd stage	$\leq 2^{-4}$
Radiation introduced in the 3 rd stage	$\leq 2^{-1}$

Please note that the RPR design protects only the Arithmetic portion of each stage (the Compute-factor, BF-Multiplier, and Multiplexor-A modules of Figure 3.) As previously discussed, to provide complete SEU protection, we would need to triplicate the controller and either SECDED-code protect the RAM or store both the precise values and truncated estimates, and use RPR to protect the RAM.

RESULTS, CONCLUSIONS, AND FUTURE WORK

The objective of this effort was the creation of a FFT structure that would be implemented in a FPGA, adopting two different methods of redundancy, TMR and RPR. The purpose was to investigate the capabilities of RPR. First a simple 64-point Radix-4 in-place FFT was implemented that could handle fixed point, 2's complement numbers and was simulated with accurate results. Next, a TMR structure was designed by replicating three identical FFT structures and by importing a voter at the end of each FFT stage. The next step was the design of a RPR structure with a degree of 8/32. The design was successfully implemented, but it failed to protect the system against radiation. Taking into consideration the problems from the previous unsuccessful design, the construction of a new RPR structure with a degree of 14/32 was conducted and resulted in a design that worked correctly and managed to protect the FFT structure efficiently.

The efforts for implementing a TMR version of the FFT in the Virtex II XC2V6000 were not successful, forcing the use of the next larger FPGA, the XC2V8000. In order to compare TMR and RPR modules, the same FPGA chip had to be used, so it was essential to use a larger FPGA of the same family. Although one can conclude that the size-reduction objective of the RPR was achieved over TMR by virtue of the fact that a larger FPGA was required for TMR.

First, the synthesis reports for the RPR and TMR modules were compared, as indicated in Table 3, where a significant difference in occupied resources is noted. RPR needs 74 percent of the slices that TMR uses, 76 percent of the slice flip flops, 68 percent of the four-input LUTs and 50 percent of embedded multipliers that the TMR uses. In Figure 7, the differences identified in the synthesis reports are presented.

Table 3. Synthesis Results—Comparison between RPR and TMR in a Virtex II XC2V8000-5FF1152 FPGA (Arithmetic Portions Only)

Virtex II XC2V8000	TMR module	TMR's occupancy	RPR module	RPR's occupancy
# Slices	11028	23%	8236	17%
# Slice FFs	18525	19%	14067	15%
# 4 input LUTs	17985	19%	12255	13%
# BRAMs	6	3%	6	3%
# MULT 18x18	144	85%	72	42%

Secondly, the Xilinx's XPower Analyzer was used to investigate the power that each of the modules required for operation. When the outcomes from both cases were compared, an interesting conclusion resulted. Although both systems needed the same amount of quiescent power, RPR required 19 percent less dynamic power than TMR. These results are tabulated in Table 4 and depicted in Figure 8.

Table 4. TMR Versus RPR—XPower Analyzer Results

Virtex II XC2V8000	TMR module	RPR module
Total Quiescent Power	0.13785 W	0.13785 W
Total Dynamic Power	0.17408 W	0.14079 W
Total Power	0.31193 W	0.27864 W
Junction Temperature	28.3 degrees C	27.9 degrees C

Figure 7. TMR Vs RPR Synthesis Results

Figure 8. TMR Vs RPR—XPower Analyzer Comparison

Our studies did not include comparisons between TMR and RPR where all parts of each stage are protected, i.e. when the stage controller is triplicated and the RAM protected. In that case, the controller resources would be the same for both TMR and RPR, and the RAM size would either be the same for both (if we use SECCDED,) or the RPR would be less by the ratio of three 32 bit values to one 32 bit value and two 14 bit values.

One of the major concerns about the RPR method is the size of the voter. This thesis suggests a simple alteration from the method suggested from Snodgrass [1], where there is no need for generating upper and lower bounds. Instead, the truncated value of the precise number is formed and duplicated. This alteration helps simplifying things and decreases the size of the voter, since now the voter can easily, with a bit-to-bit comparison, verify the correctness of the truncated values and with a simple addition or subtraction can output the predicted theoretical boundaries of the precise value.

Although several interesting results were obtained during this research relative to the specific structure chosen (the 64-point Radix-4 in-place FFT), some conclusions with broad general impact should also be mentioned. These findings can be summarized by the following statements: the RPR method is sufficient to protect against large-magnitude errors, it requires fewer resources, and is more power efficient than TMR when considering arithmetic operations. Additionally, with RPR, there are reduced resource requirements and power consumption over TMR, but there is a sacrifice in precision.

Future Work. The current structure of this design did not permit a further decrease in RPR degree, but the addition of an intelligent overflow manipulator in each stage would allow abandonment of the high RPR degree and permit

protection of each stage with the same small amount of bits that are desired. This would enable further investigation of the impact of RPR degree, and assist in understanding the trade-off of RPR degree versus precision, FFT size, and power consumption.

One concept for an intelligent overflow manipulator is to use the bit-number of the most significant bit of the value along with its sign as the RPR representation. One then duplicates this representation as was done in the fixed-point RPR FFT discussed earlier in this paper to detect errors in the precise or RPR version. This technique is currently under investigation at the Naval Postgraduate School.

It was only possible to study the effect of radiation-induced faults via simulation. To verify the effectiveness of the RPR technique in a 32-bit fixed-point FFT, testing in a controlled-radiation environment is desirable and is planned by the authors.

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BIOGRAPHIES

Athanasios Gavros is a Lieutenant (junior grade) in the Hellenic Navy currently serving at sea. He received the Bachelor of Naval Science degree from the Hellenic Naval Academy in 2003 and served in various engineering billets afloat. In 2007 he was selected to attend the U.S. Naval Postgraduate School in Monterey, CA. He graduated with a Master of Science in Electrical Engineering in September 2010.

Herschel Loomis was born in Wilmington, Delaware. He graduated from Wilmington Friends School in 1952. He received the B. E. E. Degree from Cornell University in 1957, the M. S. in Electrical Engineering from the University of Maryland in 1959 and the Ph.D. degree from Massachusetts Institute of Technology in 1963. From 1957 until 1959 he served as an electronic engineer with the United States Navy. He was Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, and Professor of Electrical and Computer Engineering at the University of California, Davis, California from 1963 until 1981. He served as Department Chairman at UC Davis from 1970 until 1975. From 1981 to 1983, he was Naval Electronics Systems Command Chair Professor at the Naval Postgraduate School in Monterey. He was Chairman of the Electrical and Computer Engineering Department of the Naval Postgraduate School from 1995 until June 1998. In September 2010 he was awarded the title of Distinguished Professor of Electrical and Computer Engineering and Space Systems. He is a retired Captain in the U. S. Naval Reserve (Cryptology). His teaching and research interests are Digital Computer Design Methodology, Digital Computer Design, Signal Processing Applications of Computers, Space Systems, High Performance Computer Architectures, reconfigurable and reliable computers, and Maritime Domain Awareness. He holds two patents and has authored over 70 technical publications. Dr. Loomis is a registered Electrical Engineer in the State of California and is a Life Senior Member of the IEEE and a member of the Association for Computing Machinery, Eta Kappa Nu, Phi Kappa Phi, Sigma Xi and Tau Beta Pi.

Alan Ross is a Professor of the Practice of Computer Engineering at the Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey, Ca. He has been associated with NPS since 1996. He was on active duty with the United States Air Force from 5 April 1966 to 1 August 1988, retiring as a Lieutenant Colonel. From

1988 to 1998 He was a Founding Partner and Vice President of Welkin Associates, Ltd., and a consultant to the Naval Research Lab, where he was the system engineer for the development of a special purpose processor system for a space application. Dr Ross has a PhD in Computer Engineering from the University of California, Davis, and a Masters in Electrical Engineering from the Air Force Institute of Technology.